

EPM 21NRM05 STASIS

Standardisation for Safe Implant Scanning

Deliverable D4: Report on the technical specifications and guidelines for comprehensive testing of gradient-induced heating of passive implants

Lead partner for the deliverable: INRIM, Istituto Nazionale di Ricerca Metrologica

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Report of Activities

1 Introduction

This report shows the results aimed at developing standardised procedures to investigate the interaction of metallic implants with the gradient magnetic fields in the kilohertz range produced by the x, y and z gradient coils (GC) of the MR system. This goal is pursued by adopting a 2-Tiers approach where: (a) Tier 1 is based on the extension of the existing ISO/TS 10974 standard for active implants [1] to the heating of passive implants caused by gradient fields, (b) Tier 2 explores further extensions of the previously analysed procedure, suitable to avoid over-conservative results when compared with realistic heating due to GC fields. The feasibility of the extensive use of numerical simulations previously validated by experiments is also considered for the purpose. In particular, it is demonstrated the possibility to extend the concepts and procedures envisaged by the current version of ISO/TS 10974, dealing with patients' protection from harm caused by gradient-induced heating of active implantable medical device enclosures and other conductive internal components to passive implants (orthopaedic implants and fixation devices). Furthermore, a Tier 2 approach is elaborated by extending the metric adopted in ISO/TS 10974 (i.e., the root-mean-square value of the magnitude of the time-derivative of the magnetic flux density) to make it suitable to quantify the heating risk of implants with complex anisotropic shapes in the presence of the superposition of more than one GC signal (axis). Compared to the previously analysed Tier 1 procedure, the Tier 2 approach avoids over-conservative results when compared with realistic heating due to GC fields. The applicability of an extensive use of numerical simulations is considered for Tier 2, after a successful validation of the computational tools versus experiments. Comparison with heating under realistic exposure scenarios in MRI and by consideration of uncertainty factors, enabled to assess how overestimation of risk evaluation can be avoided. Moreover, general concepts for excluding classes of small passive implants from testing are defined identifying those which can be considered intrinsically safe.

This document summarizes the activities of Tasks 3.1 and 3.2.

2 Implant Selection

The following implants have been selected:

- **Hip implant:** Implant manufactured by Adler Ortho SpA, Italy (model APTA-FIX + FIXA Ti-Por) with CoCrMo sphere, Ti+HA stem, Ti6Al4V cup and UHMW-PE liner (Figure 1a). Both the CAD and physical models are available at INRIM
- **Knee implant:** Implant manufactured by Adler Ortho SpA, Italy (model GENUS MB) with CoCrMo femoral and tibial components and UHMW-PE liner (Figure 1b). Both the CAD and physical models are available at INRIM

- **Shoulder implant:** Implant manufactured by LimaCorporate SpA, Italy (model TRAUMA SMR Anatomic) made in Ti6Al4V alloy (Figure 1c). Both the CAD and physical models are available at INRIM
- **Cranial plate:** Implant manufactured by Medartis AG, Switzerland (model M2-7093S) made in titanium (ASTM F67), semi-rigid. The plate is 100 mm × 100 mm and 0.6 mm thick (Figure 1d). Both the CAD and physical models are available at INRIM
- **Ankle plate:** Implant manufactured by Medartis AG, Switzerland (model 4954 25S (left)) made in titanium (ASTM F136), alloy. Together with the ankle plate, two titanium (ASTM F136) screws are considered (models 5901 50 and 5800 60) (Figure 1e). Both the CAD and physical models are available at INRIM

The electric and thermal properties of the material composing the above implants are listed in Table 1. All the physical implants related to the CAD models of Figure 1 are shown in Figure 2.

The activity reported in this section refers to activity A3.1.1

Table 1: Material electric and thermal properties

Material	El. Cond. (MS m ⁻¹)	El. Rel. Perm.	Th. Cond. (W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Sp. Heat Cap. (J kg ⁻¹ K ⁻¹)	Mass Dens. kg/m ³
Ti-6Al-4V	0.595	-	6.6	580	4420
CoCrMo	1.16	-	14	450	8445
UHMW-PE	0	2.3	0.47	1900	940

3 Exposure Scenarios Selection

Four MRI sequences have been selected for simulations. The selection was based on previous experience related to the heating potential of the different MRI sequences analysed during the relevant research activity [2].

- TrueFisp
- EPIx
- EPIy
- EPIz

The last three sequences represent the same sequence where the direction of the frequency encoding gradient (the main responsible for gradient heating of the implants) is oriented according to the last letter of the sequence name.

The implants have been positioned inside the Glenn human model trying to obtain a realistic positioning. In order to make the simulation model more general, the human model has been simulated as a homogeneous phantom with thermal properties equal to those of the ASTM gel (specific heat capacity: 4152 J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹, thermal conductivity: 0.54 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹). The use of an anatomical model was considered just to guarantee the correct positioning of the implant within the coils. To limit the size of the simulation domain, for each implant a box extending 10 cm from all sides of the implant

(a) Adler Ortho SpA hip implant CAD (b) Adler Ortho SpA knee implant CAD (c) LimaCorporate SpA shoulder implant CAD

(d) Medartis AG cranial plate CAD (e) Medartis AG ankle plate CAD

Figure 1: CAD models of the implants

(a) Adler Ortho SpA hip implant (b) Adler Ortho SpA knee im- (c) LimaCorporate SpA shoulder
plant implant

(d) Medartis AG cranial plate (e) Medartis AG ankle plate

Figure 2: Photos of the five implants collected in INRIM

Figure 3: Implant positioning inside the Glenn human model before it has been made homogeneous

bounding box has been identified. The human body has then been trimmed to be fully included by that box. The implant positioning inside Glenn human body are shown in Figure 3 before the model has been made homogeneous.

Each implant has been simulated inside a three-axial gradient coil with whole-body access (model: Solaris-R, by Nanjing Cichen Medical Technology Co., Ltd, Nanjing, China) in five different axial positions complying to realistic positions that the implants can have inside an MRI scanner. A home-made code has been used for all the simulations.

The obtained results are here collected in Figure 5 as bar plots. For each implant, the temperature increase following the application of the specific sequence repeated for 1800 s are reported. The Glenn human model has been positioned in the centre of the gradient coils (see Figure 4). The positions are therefore relevant to Glenn displacements along the z -axis of the coils.

Starting from the worst-exposure positions identified in Figure 5, the relevant implants, together with the phantom, have been moved with a 5 cm step to identify the positions in a more precise way. The outcome of the simulations are provided in Table 2.

The activity described in this section refers to activity A3.1.2

Figure 4: Model of Glenn in position 0 m with all the implants in place and a representation of the gradient coils

Table 2: Worst-exposure conditions for the five implants simulated. Data refer to 1800 s of exposure.

Implant	Sequence	Position (m)	Temperature Increase (K)
Hip	TrueFisp	-0.35	0.821
	EPIx	-0.35	1.767
	EPIy	-0.35	1.303
	EPIz	-0.4	1.603
Shoulder	TrueFisp	-0.2	0.526
	EPIx	-0.15	1.580
	EPIz	-0.25	1.169
Knee	TrueFisp	0.7	0.567
	EPIx	0	0.365
	EPIy	0.1	1.142
Ankle Plate	EPIz	0.1	1.910
	TrueFisp	0.4	0.006
	EPIx	0.4	0.002
Cranial Plate	EPIy	0.4	0.001
	EPIz	0.4	0.002
	TrueFisp	-1.15	0.215
	EPIx	-1.2	0.292
	EPIy	-1.2	0.129
	EPIz	-1.15	0.538

Figure 5: Maximum temperature increases recorded after 1800s of implant exposure to the gradient magnetic field generated by the MRI sequences. The dashed lines represent the maximum temperature increase recorded for the specific implant and sequences. Each implant has been simulated inside the homogenised Glenn human model

4 Definition of Worst-case Exposure

The activity is divided into two parts. In a first part, the orientation of the magnetic field that maximises the temperature increase after 30 min is numerically computed for all the five implants selected in section 2. In a second part, the temperature increase after 30 min is computed considering the realistic exposure scenarios identified in section 4. The activity aims at comparing the results obtained following the procedure suggested in the ISO/TS 10974:2018 standard with those that would be obtained in realistic conditions. The comparison can be performed normalising the worst-orientation results to the same *Stress Index* (as defined in the following) computed for the realistic exposure.

4.1 Worst Orientation Analysis

Theory

Let's consider the following quadratic form (see also [3]):

$$r = B^H Q B$$

where r is a real scalar, B is a real vector and Q is a symmetric matrix. Let's suppose we want to find the maximum value of r constrained to $\|B\| = 1$. Since Q is symmetric, its eigenvectors represent a base for R^n . Considering that:

$$V \lambda^D = Q V$$

where V is the eigenvector matrix (each column is a different eigenvector of Q), $V^{-1} = V^T$ and λ^D is the diagonal matrix made of the eigenvalues of Q , and we can express B as:

$$B = V \alpha$$

where α are proper real coefficients, it follows that we want to solve the following maximisation problem:

$$\max_{\alpha} \alpha^T \lambda^D \alpha \quad \text{with} \quad \|B\|^2 = \alpha^T \alpha = 1$$

Using the Lagrangian multipliers, we can focus on:

$$\nabla \mathcal{L}(\alpha, \lambda^{\mathcal{L}}) = 0$$

where $\lambda^{\mathcal{L}}$ is the Lagrangian multiplier:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{L}(\alpha, \lambda^{\mathcal{L}}) &= \frac{1}{2} \alpha^T \lambda^D \alpha - \lambda^{\mathcal{L}} g(\alpha) \\ g(\alpha) &= \alpha^T \alpha - 1 \end{aligned}$$

We obtain the following system:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha^T \lambda^D - 2\lambda^{\mathcal{L}} \alpha^T = 0 \\ \alpha^T \alpha = 1 \end{cases}$$

As an example, if Q is a 3x3 matrix:

$$\begin{cases} \alpha_1 \lambda_1 = 2\lambda^{\mathcal{L}} \alpha_1 \\ \alpha_2 \lambda_2 = 2\lambda^{\mathcal{L}} \alpha_2 \\ \alpha_3 \lambda_3 = 2\lambda^{\mathcal{L}} \alpha_3 \\ \alpha_1^2 + \alpha_2^2 + \alpha_3^2 = 1 \end{cases}$$

The above system of equations has three solutions:

$$\begin{cases} s_1 = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \lambda^{\mathcal{L}}) = (\pm 1, 0, 0, \lambda_1/2) \\ s_2 = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \lambda^{\mathcal{L}}) = (0, \pm 1, 0, \lambda_2/2) \\ s_3 = (\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \alpha_3, \lambda^{\mathcal{L}}) = (0, 0, \pm 1, \lambda_3/2) \end{cases}$$

Considering that these solutions will lead to a $r = r^n$ of the form:

$$r_n = \lambda_n \alpha_n^2 = \lambda_n$$

we obtain that the maximum r_n will be:

$$r_{max} = \lambda_1 \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda_1 \geq \lambda_2 \geq \lambda_3$$

and the B vector that maximises the r value will be the eigenvector associated with the maximum eigenvalue, *i.e.* λ_1

This procedure can be applied to find the worst exposure direction since both the power deposited by a harmonic magnetic field into a generic implant and the consequent temperature rise can be expressed by proper quadratic forms. In particular, we can express the current density vector J generated in a point by a harmonic magnetic field H as:

$$J = \sum_i j_i^u H_i = [J]H$$

where j_i^u is the current density vector generated by a unitary magnetic field along the i -th Cartesian direction, H_i is the i -th component of the magnetic field and $[J]$ is a 3×3 matrix with the j_i^u as columns. Since we are interested in linearly polarised magnetic field, $H_i \in R^n$ for $i=1, \dots, 3$. The local power density p can be obtained as:

$$p = \Re \left[\frac{1}{\sigma} J^H J \right] = \frac{1}{\sigma} H^T \Re [[J]^H [J]] H \quad (1)$$

where σ is the electrical conductivity in $S m^{-1}$. The total power deposited inside the implant will be:

$$P = \int_{Vol} p dV = H^T \int_{Vol} \frac{1}{\sigma} \Re [[J]^H [J]] dV H = H^T Q H \quad (2)$$

The temperature increase inside the implant is proportional to the power density, from 1 it is possible to express the temperature rise in each voxel as a quadratic forms as well:

$$\Delta T = \mathcal{L}_T[p] = H^T M H \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{L}_T is the linear operator solving the heat equation, which depends on the thermal conductivity and heat capacity of the device under test (DUT) and the thermal characteristics of the surrounding environment. Since M is symmetric, the m, n component is equal to the conjugate of the n, m component, for any $n, m=1, \dots, 3$ and they result to be equal to the temperature rise distribution following the application of a fictitious power density distribution equal to:

$$p = \frac{1}{\sigma} \Re [j_n^{u*} j_m^u]$$

Results

The previous procedure has been applied to compute the magnetic field orientation that maximises the power deposition and the temperature rise into the implants selected in section 2, with exception

Table 3: Power worst orientation obtained with the home-made code at 270 Hz

Implant	H_x (A m ⁻¹)	H_y (A m ⁻¹)	H_z (A m ⁻¹)	θ (°)	ϕ (°)	P (nW)
Hip	-0.34	-0.69	0.63	50.63	-116	3.83
Knee	0.01	0.21	0.98	11.93	88.12	4.62
Knee - Tibial	0.00	-0.01	1.00	0.73	-91.2	2.62
Knee - Femur	0.02	0.63	0.78	38.86	88.04	2.36
Shoulder	0.65	-0.34	0.68	47.33	-27.43	0.75
Ankle Plate (No screws)	-0.69	0.72	0.07	85.91	133.58	0.18
Ankle Plate (Conf. 1)	-0.69	0.72	0.07	85.75	133.49	0.18
Cranial plate	0	0	1	0	0	0.8

Table 4: Power worst orientation obtained with Sim4Life at 270 Hz

Implant	H_x (A m ⁻¹)	H_y (A m ⁻¹)	H_z (A m ⁻¹)	θ (°)	ϕ (°)	P (nW)
Hip	-0.34	-0.7	0.63	50.65	-115.99	3.81
Knee	0.01	0.22	0.97	12.98	88.01	4.18
Knee - Tibial	0.00	-0.01	1.00	0.54	90	2.55
Knee - Femur	0.02	0.62	0.78	38.41	88.17	2.36
Shoulder	0.65	-0.34	0.68	47.41	-27.46	0.75
Ankle Plate (No screws)	-0.69	0.72	0.07	85.95	133.55	0.17
Ankle Plate (Conf. 1)	-0.69	0.72	0.07	85.7	133.51	0.18

of the cranial plate where, being a 2D implant, the direction normal to its surface is already known to be the worst. As regards the ankle plate, due to the effect that the mounting screws could have, two configurations have been accounted for: with and without the screws. The temperature increase has been evaluated for 5 min to 30 min storing the distribution every 5 min. All the results, except for those with the cranial plate, have been obtained both with a home-made simulation code and with Sim4Life. As regards the latter tool, Python scripts have been produced to automatise the procedure within the software interface. Finally, the cranial plate has been simulated only with the home-made coil since a specific procedure has been applied to avoid unmanageable computational burdens [4]. The results are collected in Table 3, 4, 5 and 6 where the worst direction is expressed in polar coordinates being θ the polar angle and ϕ the azimuthal angle. As regards the temperature results, simulations have been carried out with the implants placed inside a phantom (Specific Heat Capacity: 4152 J kg⁻¹ K⁻¹, Thermal Conductivity: 0.54 W m⁻¹ K⁻¹) whose faces are insulated with respect to the surrounding air (*i.e.*, adiabatic conditions)

In addition to the worst-orientation analysis, the quadratic expression derived for each implant allows to efficiently compute the power deposited into the implant (by means of equation 2) or the following temperature increase (by means of equation 3) due to an exposure to an arbitrary magnetic field. As an example, in Figure 6 the power and maximum temperature increase at different time instants is shown as a function of the magnetic field direction at 270 Hz.

4.2 Comparison between ISO Tier 1 testing experiment and realistic scenarios

In order to assess the degree of temperature overestimation introduced by the ISO/TS 10974 procedure when testing for gradient induced heating, the results of Table 2 are compared with the results of Table 5. For doing this, the results of Table 5 have been scaled with equation (4). This corresponds to

Table 5: 1800sec temperature increase worst orientation obtained with the home-made code and following a 270 Hz homogeneous magnetic field exposure

Implant	H_x ($A m^{-1}$)	H_y ($A m^{-1}$)	H_z ($A m^{-1}$)	θ ($^\circ$)	ϕ ($^\circ$)	ΔT (nK)
Hip	-0.19	-0.70	0.69	46.14	-105.25	9.25
Knee	0.00	-0.03	1.00	1.83	-88.88	10.4
Knee - Tibial	0.00	-0.08	1.00	4.34	90.4	8.96
Knee - Femur	0.02	0.48	0.88	28.7	88.08	7.17
Shoulder	0.66	-0.36	0.66	48.6	-28.97	3.31
Ankle Plate (No screws)	-0.74	0.61	0.30	72.83	140.7	0.41
Ankle Plate (Conf. 1)	-0.74	0.61	0.31	72.23	140.55	0.41
Cranial plate	0	0	1	0	0	2.18

Table 6: 1800sec temperature increase worst orientation obtained with Sim4Life and following a 270 Hz homogeneous magnetic field exposure

Implant	H_x ($A m^{-1}$)	H_y ($A m^{-1}$)	H_z ($A m^{-1}$)	θ ($^\circ$)	ϕ ($^\circ$)	ΔT (nK)
Hip	-0.19	-0.7	0.69	46.18	-105.34	9.18
Knee	0.00	-0.03	1.00	1.96	-89.16	8.84
Knee - Tibial	0.00	-0.06	1.00	3.49	-90.35	7.63
Knee - Femur	0.01	0.48	0.88	28.56	88.27	7.13
Shoulder	0.63	-0.37	0.68	47.28	-30.46	3.28
Ankle Plate (No screws)	-0.74	0.6	0.3	72.49	140.85	0.38
Ankle Plate (Conf. 1)	-0.74	0.6	0.31	72	41.06	0.4

Figure 6: Power and temperature maps relative to the hip implant for a 270 Hz homogeneous magnetic field

scale the temperature increase of Table 5 at the same $(\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}|_{rms})^2$ as those of Table 2:

$$\Delta T'_{iso} = \Delta T_{iso} \frac{2I}{(2\pi\mu_0 270)^2} \quad (4)$$

where $\Delta T'_{iso}$ is the scaled temperature increase and ΔT_{iso} is the temperature increase as in Table 5 obtained for a magnetic field with 1 A m^{-1} amplitude at 270 Hz. I represents the stress index, computed in the implant barycentre, as proposed in [2] and accounting for the non-linear polarisation of the magnetic field during the sequence execution:

$$I(\mathbf{x}_b) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \frac{1}{TR} \underbrace{\int_0^{TR} \frac{dG_i}{dt}(t) \frac{dG_j}{dt}(t) dt}_{S_{ij}} \mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_b) \cdot \mathbf{B}_j(\mathbf{x}_b)$$

where S_{ij} is the ij entry of a positive semi-definite S matrix which is related to the considered MRI sequence. $\mathbf{B}_i(\mathbf{x}_b)$ is the magnetic flux density in \mathbf{x}_b (the implant barycentre) generated by the i -th gradient coil when supplied to generate a 1 T m^{-1} gradient in its isocentre. The S matrices are:

$$S_{TrueFisp} = \begin{pmatrix} 2888 & -16 & -448 \\ -16 & 1166 & 0 \\ -448 & 0 & 3150 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S_{EPIx} = \begin{pmatrix} 10928 & 60 & -6 \\ 60 & 161 & -1 \\ -6 & -1 & 698 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S_{EPIy} = \begin{pmatrix} 698 & -6 & -1 \\ -6 & 10928 & 60 \\ -1 & 60 & 161 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$S_{EPIz} = \begin{pmatrix} 161 & -1 & 60 \\ -1 & 698 & -6 \\ 60 & -6 & 10928 \end{pmatrix}$$

The comparison between the temperature increase after 1800 s of exposure to four realistic MRI sequences and those resulting from an ISO Tier 1 testing at the same $\frac{\partial B}{\partial t}|_{rms}$ are reported in Table 7. The maximum ratio between the two temperature increases is found for the Cranial Plate and the EPIz sequence and amounts to 0.88. The lowest ratios are found for the Ankle Plate where the temperature increases are anyway negligible. The ratios reported in Table 7 are also showed in Figure 7.

The results shown in this section refer to activity A3.1.4

5 Temperature increase experiments

Experiments have been carried out using both an ad hoc testing exposure system, available at MR:COMP, and another laboratory setup provided with a realistic gradient coil set, available at INRIM.

5.1 Measurements at MR:COMP

According to the indications provided by INRIM, MR:COMP carried out the experiments with three specimens: the femoral component of a knee implant, the tibial component of a knee implant and a shoulder implant. The above components are those selected in section 4 and are shown in Figure 2b and Figure 2c. The orientation of the specimens inside the MR:COMP's exposure system and the

Figure 7: Ratios between the temperature increase after 1800s of exposure to four realistic MRI sequences and those resulting from an ISO testing at the same $\frac{\partial B}{\partial t} |_{rms}$

Table 7: Comparison between the temperature increase after 1800 s of exposure to four realistic MRI sequences and those resulting from an ISO Tier 1 testing experiment at the same $\left. \frac{\partial B}{\partial t} \right|_{rms}$

Implant	Sequence	Position (cm)	ΔT_{seq} (K)	$\Delta T'_{iso}$ (K)	$\Delta T_{seq}/\Delta T'_{iso}$
Hip	TrueFisp	-0.35	0.821	1.496	0.55
	EPIx	-0.35	1.767	3.009	0.59
	EPIy	-0.35	1.303	2.563	0.51
	EPIz	-0.4	1.603	2.979	0.54
Shoulder	TrueFisp	-0.2	0.526	1.109	0.47
	EPIx	-0.15	1.580	2.234	0.71
	EPIy	-0.25	0.429	1.270	0.34
	EPIz	-0.25	1.169	1.931	0.61
Knee	TrueFisp	0.7	0.567	1.780	0.32
	EPIx	0	0.365	3.604	0.10
	EPIy	0.1	1.142	2.804	0.41
	EPIz	0.1	1.910	3.08	0.61
Ankle Plate	TrueFisp	0.4	0.006	0.013	0.46
	EPIx	0.4	0.002	0.031	0.07
	EPIy	0.4	0.001	0.019	0.05
	EPIz	0.4	0.002	0.021	0.09
Cranial Plate	TrueFisp	-1.15	0.215	0.321	0.67
	EPIx	-1.2	0.292	0.587	0.50
	EPIy	-1.2	0.129	0.563	0.23
	EPIz	-1.15	0.538	0.611	0.88

position of the temperature probes have been chosen according to the results obtained in section 5 (see Table 5). In addition, MR:COMP carried out a preliminary investigation exposing the specimens to a 2500 Hz magnetic field with a $dB/dt_{RMS} = 50.15 \text{ T s}^{-1}$. The specimens have been exposed for 300 s in air and the temperature distribution on their surfaces has been recorded through an infrared camera. The temperature distribution has been accounted for to define the thermal probe positions.

Once the temperature probes have been positioned in the identified positions, the specimens have been plunged into a gel prepared according to the ISO/TS 10974:2018 (see the first column of table L.2 of the standard). The gel has been radiated by a 1750 Hz magnetic field with a $dB/dt_{RMS} = 42 \text{ T s}^{-1}$ for 30 min as suggested by the ISO/TS 10974:2018 standard and by its third edition, which is intended to be published as an international standard and is currently available as a draft version.

Table 8: Properties of the simulated gel phantom

Density (kg m^{-3})	1000
Heat Capacity ($\text{kJ kg}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	4.17
Thermal Conductivity ($\text{W m}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)	0.624

The same exposure conditions have been reproduced in a simulation environment. The properties of the phantom are collected in Table 8. All the simulations have been performed with a home-made code. A preliminary check on the physical dimensions and properties of the specimens, brought to light some minor discrepancies between the implants and the relevant CAD models. In particular the following modifications have been implemented on the CAD models described in section 2 and represented in Figure 1:

- The humeral head of the shoulder implant has been simulated as CrCoMo alloy instead of Ti6Al4V;

- The thickness of the tibial plate of the knee implant has been revised;
- The old femoral component CAD has been substituted by a new one obtained by means of 3D scanning of the physical object.

Table 9: Measurement and simulation results together with their expanded uncertainties ($k = 2$)

	ΔT Measurements	ΔT Simulations	Relative difference
Shoulder Ch0	3.50(52) K	3.88(32) K	-10.3 %
Shoulder Ch1	3.97(59) K	4.02(33) K	-1.25 %
Shoulder Ch2	3.73(55) K	4.02(33) K	-7.48 %
Knee Tibial Ch0	5.60(83) K	4.74(63) K	16.6 %
Knee Tibial Ch1	5.88(87) K	5.11(68) K	14.01 %
Knee Femoral Ch0	5.63(84) K	5.00(79) K	11.85 %
Knee Femoral Ch1	7.34(109) K	7.23(114) K	1.52 %
Knee Femoral Ch2	5.64(84) K	5.08(80) K	10.45 %

The measurements and simulation results are collected in Table 9 where Ch0, Ch1 and Ch2 refers to the measurement channels; *i.e.*, the measurement points. The table also reports the relative difference between the measurement and simulation best estimates.

As regards the uncertainty contributions, the uncertainty related to the measurements is described in the relevant report circulated by MR:COMP among the partner and whose content has to remain confidential [5]. The uncertainty related to the model is obtained by considering the following measurement model:

$$\Delta T_{\text{imp}}^{\text{sim}} = \overline{\Delta T}_{\text{imp}}^{\text{sim}} C_{\text{rot}} C_{\text{amp}}$$

where:

1. $\Delta T_{\text{imp}}^{\text{sim}}$ is the measurand: the temperature increase on an implant position;
2. $\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{imp}}^{\text{sim}}$ is the average temperature increase in an implant point between the same simulation performed with Sim4Life and a home-made code, previously validated by comparison with experiments [2]. Its standard deviation has been computed as it follows. The same simulation has been repeated with Sim4Life and the home-made code. The maximum difference between the two results looking at all temperature sensors and at the last time point has been considered as a uniform interval within which the true simulated value lies. Therefore, the standard deviation has been obtained as the difference between the extreme temperature data divided by $\sqrt{12}$;
3. C_{rot} accounts for the uncertain object rotation with respect to the experimental reference. It has a unit average value and its standard deviation has been computed as it follows. For each specimen the maximum temperature increase has been computed for an exposure to a reference homogeneous harmonic magnetic field oriented along the worst direction. A variation of the magnetic field direction has been applied according to a uniform $\pm 2^\circ$ angle distribution. The standard deviation of the maximum temperature increase defines the uncertainty contribution applied for each sensor related to the relevant specimen;
4. C_{amp} accounts for the uncertainty in the object positioning inside the exposure system. It has a unit average value and its standard deviation has been computed as it follows. For each specimen the maximum temperature increase has been computed for an exposure to a reference homogeneous harmonic magnetic field oriented along the worst direction. A position inside a cylinder (4 cm radius and 8 cm height) sitting inside the exposure system has been extracted according to a uniform distribution. The magnetic field in that point has been used to compute the maximum temperature increase on the reference specimen when exposed to a homogeneous

Table 10: Contributions to model uncertainty

Implant	$\Delta T_{\text{imp}}^{\text{sim}}$	C_{rot}	C_{amp}
Shoulder	3.3 %	0.8 %	2.3 %
Knee Tibial	6.2 %	0.4 %	2.5 %
Knee Femoral	7.5 %	1 %	2.3 %

harmonic magnetic field with such an amplitude. The standard deviation of the maximum temperature increase defines the uncertainty contribution applied for each sensor related to the relevant specimen;

Table 10 collects the different contributions to the numerical uncertainty for each implant.

Figure 8 shows the comparisons between the experiments conducted by MR:COMP and the relevant simulations performed with the home-made code. The error bars refer to the expanded uncertainties.

5.2 Measurements at INRIM

The activity has been developed in two stages. In a first stage the specimens have been positioned and oriented inside the INRIM GC set-up according to a position aiming at maximise the GC induced heating. A harmonic field has been generated and the temperature increase in different points of the specimens has been recorded and compared to analogous simulations. The aim of this experimental phase was to test the positioning capability of the specimens, optimise the matching of the electrical and thermal properties of the specimens between real implants and CAD models and check the accuracy of the GC model available for simulations.

In the second stage, the specimens have been positioned and radiated according to the realistic exposure conditions identified in section 3. The recorded temperature increase has been compared with numerical simulations. All the experiments have been carried out into the ASTM gel phantom whose simulated properties corresponds to those in Table 8.

Stage 1 – Worst Condition

The measurements involved the following specimens:

1. Shoulder implant;
2. Hip implant;
3. Knee Tibial component;
4. Knee Femoral component;

Table 11 collects the list of measured implants and conditions. All experiments have been carried out by exposing the specimens to a harmonic magnetic field at 1750 Hz. Previous investigations showed that the skin effect is not significant at this frequency value. Therefore both Sim4Life and a home-made numerical code could be used for simulations. Figure 9 shows the comparisons between the measured and simulated temperature increases for each sensor and experiment listed in Table 11.

(a) Shoulder implant measurement channel Ch0 (b) Shoulder implant measurement channel Ch1 (c) Shoulder implant measurement channel Ch2

(d) Tibial component measurement channel Ch0 (e) Tibial component measurement channel Ch1 (f) Femoral component measurement channel Ch0

(g) Femoral component measurement channel Ch1 (h) Femoral component measurement channel Ch2

Figure 8: Comparison between measured results (MR:COMP) and simulated results (home-made code). Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)

Table 11: Worst conditions experiments. "sin <a> <f>" identifies a harmonic field generated by supplying the gradient coils with a current of amplitude <a> A and frequency <f> Hz. The field "Coils" identifies the gradient coils that have been supplied during the experiment

Implant	Position (m)	Sequence	Coils	Duration (s)	N° sensors
Shoulder Implant	0.164, 0.007, 0.3	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3
Knee Femoral Component	0.162, 0.008, 0.291	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3
Hip Implant	0.174, -0.048, 0.3	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3
Knee Tibial Plate	0.171, 0, 0.3	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3

(a) Shoulder implant - Ch0

(b) Shoulder implant - Ch1

(c) Shoulder implant - Ch2

(d) Knee Femoral component - Ch0

(e) Knee Femoral component - Ch1

(f) Knee Femoral component - Ch2

(g) Knee Tibial component - Ch0

(h) Knee Tibial component - Ch1

(i) Knee Tibial component - Ch2

(j) Hip implant - Ch0

(k) Hip implant - Ch1

(l) Hip implant - Ch2

Figure 9: Comparison between measured results and simulated results. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$)

Stage 2 – Realistic Exposure

The measurements involved the following specimens:

1. Shoulder implant;
2. Hip implant;
3. Knee Tibial component;
4. Knee Femoral component;
5. Knee implant

where "Knee implant" comprised both the tibial and femoral components interleaved with the liner. Table 12 collects the list of measured implants and conditions. The waveform of the sequences considered for the experiments are represented in Figure 10. Such sequences are different from those used in section 3 due to hardware limitation. Figures 11, 12, and 13 show the comparisons between the measured and simulated temperature increases for each sensor and experiment listed in Table 12. The z-position of the implants complies with the worst axial positions of Glenn as simulated in section 3 (see Table 2). In particular, the experiments refer to the scenarios listed in Table 13. When the specimens have been exposed to a harmonic magnetic field, simulations have been carried out with Sim4Life and a home-made code. To simulate the skin effect, that could affect the results for the highest harmonics of the sequence waveforms, simulations where the specimens have been exposed to the magnetic field generated by a realistic sequence have been carried out with the home-made code.

Table 12: Realistic exposure experiments. "sin <a><f>" identifies a harmonic field generated by supplying the gradient coils with a current of amplitude <a> A and frequency <f> Hz. The field "Coils" identifies the gradient coils that have been supplied during the experiment

Implant	Experiment ID	Position (m)	Sequence	Coils	Duration (s)	N° sensors	dB/dt rms ($T s^{-1}$)
Shoulder Implant	E1	-0.173, -0.003, 0.391	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3	30.83
Shoulder Implant	E2	-0.173, -0.003, 0.391	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	X, Y, Z	970	3	26.20
Knee Implant Complete	E1	0.088, 0.009, -0.311	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	5	23.61
Knee Implant Complete	E2	0.088, 0.009, -0.311	EPIz SR110 delay10ms	X, Y, Z	420	5	18.86
Knee Femoral Component	E1	0.088, -0.001, -0.301	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3	23.46
Knee Tibial Plate	E1	0.087, 0, -0.3	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3	23.85
Hip Implant	E1	-0.092, 0.015, -0.284	sin 150 1750	X, Z	970	3	24.78
Hip Implant	E2	-0.092, 0.015, -0.284	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	X, Y, Z	420	3	20.00
Hip Implant	E3	-0.092, 0.015, -0.284	TrueFisp SR130	X, Y, Z	420	3	18.45

Table 13: Measured scenarios with reference to Table 2 of section 3

Implant	Glenn Position	Sequence
Hip	-0.35 m	EPIx
Hip	-0.35 m	TrueFisp
Shoulder	-0.15 m	EPIx
Knee	0.1 m	EPIz

Uncertainty Budget – Experimental data

The uncertainty model associated to the experimental data is given by:

$$\Delta T(t) = \overline{\Delta T}(t) C_{\text{rep}}^{\text{imp}} C_{\text{var}}^{\text{imp, ch}}$$

where:

1. $\Delta T(t)$ is the measurand: the temperature increase in a specific implant point at a generic time instant;
2. $\overline{\Delta T}(t)$ is the measured temperature increase resulting from averaging multiple measurements performed for the same specimen, in the same position and exposed to the same magnetic field. Its standard deviation accounts for the measurement noise in the following way. Each temperature increase time trend has been subtracted by its moving average. The standard deviation of such a difference (σ_{noise}) has been computed and the relative standard uncertainty associated to $\overline{\Delta T}(t)$ has been computed as:

$$u_r[\overline{\Delta T}(t)] = \frac{1}{N} \frac{\sqrt{\sum_n \sigma_{\text{noise},n}^2}}{\overline{\Delta T}(t)}$$

where N is the number of performed measurements;

3. $C_{\text{rep}}^{\text{imp}}$ is a unit average coefficient whose standard deviation accounts for the repeatability of the experiments. For each implant, all repeated experiments have been grouped and the maximum difference of the temperature increases at the end of the experiment group ($t = t_f$) has been recorded (ΔT_{max}^g). The uncertainty contribution accounting for the measurement repeatability is associated to each specific implant as the maximum among ΔT_{max}^g with a uniform distribution. Therefore, the relative standard uncertainty of C_{rep} has been computed as

$$u_r[C_{\text{rep}}] = \frac{1}{\overline{\Delta T}(t = t_f)} \max_g \Delta T_{\text{max}}^g / \sqrt{12}$$

4. $C_{\text{var}}^{\text{imp, ch}}$ is a unit average coefficient whose standard deviation accounts for the volume of the sensitive part of the temperature probes. The probe manufacturer declares this to be 1 mm × 2 mm × 3 mm. Therefore, for each implant and measuring channel position, a number of temperature increase values have been extracted from simulations performed inside the boxes representing the sensitive volumes of the temperature probes. The temperature increase at the final instant of the experiment ($t = t_f$) has been considered and the relative standard deviation of the temperature increase values inside the box has been computed with respect to the temperature increase value at the centre of the box. Such standard deviation represents the relative standard uncertainty associated to the $C_{\text{var}}^{\text{imp, ch}}$ coefficient.

The relative standard uncertainty of ΔT is therefore obtained by propagating the above uncertainty contributions.

$$u_r[\Delta T(t)] = \sqrt{u_r[\overline{\Delta T}(t)]^2 + u_r[C_{\text{rep}}]^2 + u_r[C_{\text{var}}^{\text{imp, ch}}]^2} \quad (5)$$

(a) EPIx SR110 delay10ms

(b) TrueFisp SR130

Figure 10: Sequence waveforms. The sequence named "EPIz SR110 delay10ms" in Table 12 is identical to the "EPIx SR110 delay10ms" where the G_x and G_z are exchanged

(a) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch0 (b) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch1 (c) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch2

(d) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch0 (e) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch1 (f) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch2

Figure 11: Comparison between measured results and simulated results. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$). Results are relevant to the shoulder implant.

(a) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch0 (b) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch1 (c) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch3

(d) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch4 (e) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch5 (f) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch6

(g) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch0

(h) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch1

(i) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch3

(j) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch4

(k) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch5

(l) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch6

(m) Knee Femoral Component - E1 - Ch0

(n) Knee Femoral Component - E1 - Ch1

(o) Knee Femoral Component - E1 - Ch2

(p) Knee Tibial Plate - E1 - Ch0

(q) Knee Tibial Plate - E1 - Ch1

(r) Knee Tibial Plate - E1 - Ch2

Figure 12: Comparison between measured results and simulated results. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$). Results are relevant to the knee implant.

Figure 13: Comparison between measured results and simulated results. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$). Results are relevant to the hip implant.

Uncertainty Budget – Numerical Data

The uncertainty model associated to the numerical data is given by:

$$\Delta T(t) = \overline{\Delta T}(t) C_{\text{rot}}^{\text{imp}} C_{\text{amp}}^{\text{imp}}$$

where:

1. $\Delta T(t)$ is the measurand: the temperature increase in a specific implant point at a generic time instant;
2. $\overline{\Delta T}(t)$ is the simulated temperature increase in a specific implant point resulting from averaging simulation data obtained from the same model simulated by means of Sim4Life and a home-made code. Its standard deviation accounts for the difference between the results obtained through the two numerical tools. Its relative standard uncertainty has been obtained as:

$$u_r[\overline{\Delta T}(t)] = \frac{1}{\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{avg}}(t = t_f)} \frac{|\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{hm}}(t = t_f) - \overline{\Delta T}_{\text{S4L}}(t = t_f)|}{\sqrt{12}}$$

where $\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{hm}}$ and $\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{S4L}}$ indicate the temperature increase in a specific implant point as simulated with the home-made code and Sim4Life, respectively, t_f represents the final time instant of the simulated thermal evolution and $\overline{\Delta T}_{\text{avg}}$ is the average between the temperature increase values simulated with the two tools;

3. $C_{\text{rot}}^{\text{imp}}$ accounts for the uncertain object rotation with respect to the experimental reference. It has a unit average value and its relative standard uncertainty has been computed as it follows. For each implant a reference temperature increase has been computed as the maximum temperature increase for an exposure to a reference homogeneous harmonic magnetic field equal to that measured by means of a magnetic field probe at the object position inside the gradient coils. A variation of the magnetic field direction has been applied according to a uniform $\pm 2^\circ$ angle distribution. The standard deviation of the maximum temperature increase all over the implant, divided by the reference temperature increase, defined the standard relative uncertainty of $C_{\text{rot}}^{\text{imp}}$ and has been applied to each sensor related to the relevant implant;
4. $C_{\text{amp}}^{\text{imp}}$ accounts for the difference between the actual gradient coils and those that have been simulated in order to retrieve the magnetic field distribution. It has a unit average value and its relative standard uncertainty has been computed as it follows. The magnetic field generated by the three gradient coil axes has been measured by means of a magnetic field probe inside four volumes within the gradient coil. Given an experiment, the volume in which the implant has been measured has been identified and the measured magnetic field has been compared to the simulated magnetic field in the same measuring points and volume. A linear regression has been applied to the measured magnetic field versus the simulated one and the standard deviation, σ_{res} , of the residuals has been computed. The magnetic field applied during the harmonic experiments, H_{harm} , has been measured and a simulation where the implant has been exposed to such a homogeneous magnetic field has been performed. The maximum temperature increase on the implant has been recorded as reference temperature increase, ΔT_{ref} . A number of magnetic field values have been extracted from a normal distribution with standard deviation σ_{res} and average value H_{harm} . The standard deviation of the maximum temperature increases on the implant exposed to the extracted magnetic field has been divided by the reference temperature increase ΔT_{ref} and represented the relative standard uncertainty associated with $C_{\text{amp}}^{\text{imp}}$.

The results of this section refer to the activities A3.1.5 and A3.1.6

Figure 14: An example of the calculated approximation line provided for the hip implant, experiment E1 of Table 12, channel 0. The fitting line calculated with a simple least-squares method (blue line) is compared with the straight line obtained applying the ISO/TS 28037:2010 procedure (red line)

5.3 Agreement Between Experiments and Simulations

The results of the experiments carried out by INRIM and of the relevant simulations have been collected and statistically analyzed. The purpose of the analysis was to quantify the agreement between the experimental and numerical results. This outcome will be used in future activities to provide a confidence interval associated to the simulation results.

In order to achieve the result, the procedure described in the ISO/TS 28037:2010 standard has been followed: Determination and use of straight-line calibration [6]. Figure 14 shows the results relevant to the experiment carried out with the hip implant. The experiment is the E1 of Table 12, where the temperature increase is recorded for channel 0. The output data for the same example are shown in Figure 15. The output of the straight-line model (y_{calc}) is very close to the actual measured data (y_{INRIM}) especially when all the experimental data are considered (table above). Also the uncertainty values associated to the output of the straight-line model ($u(y_{calc})$) are close to those associated to the actual measurements ($u(y_{INRIM})$). This holds for all the three timestamps reported in the figure.

The results satisfy the requirements of activity A3.2.5

6 Exposure Comparison

Table 7 compares the maximum temperature increases on five implants following the execution of realistic MR experiments with those obtained executing the ISO 10974 Tier 1 testing experiment, at the same dB/dt rms. According to these data, the ISO experiment always overestimates the maximum temperature increase when the investigated passive orthopaedic implants are involved. Overestimations range from a minimum of 12%, for the Cranial Plate exposed to the time-varying magnetic field generated by the EPIz, to a maximum of 180%, for the Ankle Plate exposed to the time-varying magnetic field generated by the EPIy. Focusing only on the bulkier implants (*i.e.*, Hip, Shoulder and Knee), where the maximum temperature increases reached during the experiments are more significant,

	Calculation $y_{\text{calc}} = a + b \cdot x$		Original data from INRIM	
Time t	y_{calc}	$u(y_{\text{calc}})$	y_{INRIM}	$u(y_{\text{INRIM}})$
300 s	0.2154	0.0222	0,2145	0,0223
600 s	0.3415	0.0340	0,3460	0,0329
900 s	0.4442	0.0436	0,4585	0,0425

	Calculation $y_{\text{calc}} = a + b \cdot x$		Original data from INRIM	
Time t	y_{calc}	$u(y_{\text{calc}})$	y_{INRIM}	$u(y_{\text{INRIM}})$
300 s	0.2120	0.0240	0,2145	0,0223
600 s	0.3480	0.0367	0,3460	0,0329
900 s	0.4587	0.0470	0,4585	0,0425

Figure 15: Output data relevant to the example shown in Figure 14: hip implant, experiment E1, channel 0. The table above accounted for all the data in computing the straight-line whereas the table below neglects the temperature increase points before 120 s after the beginning of the experiment

Table 14: Comparison between the temperature increase measured by MR:COMP (MRC) and INRIM (realistic exposure experiments of Table 12) at the same dB/dt rms. "sin $\langle a \rangle \langle f \rangle$ " identifies a harmonic field generated by supplying the gradient coils with a current of amplitude $\langle a \rangle$ A and frequency $\langle f \rangle$ Hz.

Implant	Exp. ID	Sequence	ΔT_{INRIM} (K)	$\Delta T'_{\text{MRC}}$ (K)	$\Delta T_{\text{INRIM}}/\Delta T'_{\text{MRC}}$
Shoulder Implant	E1	sin 150 1750	1.3	1.62	0.8
Shoulder Implant	E2	EPIx SR110 delay 10ms	0.6	0.78	0.77
Knee Femoral	E1	sin 150 1750	0.7	1.78	0.39
Knee Tibial	E1	sin 150 1750	0.5	1.44	0.35

the minimum overestimation increases to about 35 %, in the case of the Shoulder implant exposed to the EPIx sequence. The maximum overestimation decreases to 163 %, in the case of the Knee Implant exposed to the EPIx sequence.

These outcomes are supported by the results shown in section 5. The maximum temperature increases measured for each implant by MR:COMP have been considered after a time equal to those of the experiments carried in INRIM for the same implants (*i.e.*, 970 s and 420 s for harmonic field and MR sequence experiments, respectively). Such temperature increases have been scaled in order to refer to the same dB/dt rms of the experiments carried out in INRIM (see Table 12). The results are collected in Table 14 where it is evident that the Tier 1 testing experiment of the ISO 10974 standard overestimates the maximum temperature increase of a realistic experiment from 22 % up to 97 %. In addition, the comparison between the experimental results and the numerical simulations shown in section 5 demonstrates that, taking into account the experimental and model uncertainties, numerical simulations are generally able to reliably predict the experimental outcomes.

On the basis of these considerations, the investigation of a Tier 2 approach, able to supplement the ISO/TS 10974 Tier 1 testing experiment, could be justified in order to avoid overconservative limits when dealing with gradient-switched heating of passive conductive implants.

7 Tier 2 Approach

The Tier 2 approach aims at reducing the overconservative results following the application of the switched gradient heating testing procedure suggested by the ISO/TS 10974 standard on orthopaedic implants (see Tables 7 and 14). A solution in this regard is proposed in [2] where a so-called Isotropic Stress Index is computed on the basis of the running MR sequence and gradient coil hardware for each spatial point inside the scanner:

$$I^{iso}(\vec{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 \underbrace{\frac{1}{TR} \int_0^{TR} \frac{dG_i}{dt}(t) \frac{dG_j}{dt}(t) dt}_{Q_{ij}} \vec{B}_i(\vec{x}) \vec{B}_j(\vec{x}) \quad (6)$$

where:

- $G_{i/j}$ is the gradient field in T m^{-1} generated by the i/j gradient coil;
- $\vec{B}_{i/j}(\vec{x})$ is the magnetic field produced by the i -th gradient coil in \vec{x} when the gradient at the isocenter is 1 T m^{-1} along the coil reference direction;
- TR is the sequence repetition time in s

When a reference dosimetric quantity, to be limited for safety purposes and well correlated with the Stress Index, (*e.g.*, the maximum peak temperature increase after a defined amount of time of exposure of an implant to a homogeneous harmonic magnetic field) is identified, it is possible to define a threshold on the Stress Index in order to limit such a reference dosimetric quantity.

At this stage, in order to be conservative, the reference dosimetric quantity has to account for the worst case exposure of the considered implant. For this reason, the Isotropic Stress Index leads to analogous results of the ISO/TS 10974 testing procedures with the only difference to be able of accounting for the non-linearly polarised magnetic field generated by the MR sequences. In order decrease the degree of overestimation of the safety thresholds, the actual shape of the implant has to be accounted for. This can be accomplished by introducing in the Isotropic Stress Index equation a unitless weighting coefficient η_u associated to each direction u along which the magnetic field produced by the gradient coils could be oriented.

$$I^{aniso}(\vec{x}) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \sum_{j=1}^3 Q_{ij} \eta_{B_i(x)} \eta_{B_j(x)} \vec{B}_i(\vec{x}) \vec{B}_j(\vec{x}) \quad (7)$$

The anisotropy coefficients η_u can be easily obtained by means of the numerical algorithm developed in section 4 (see equation 3). In particular:

$$\eta_u = \sqrt{\frac{D(u)}{\max_v D(v)}} \quad (8)$$

where $D(u)$ is the value of the dosimetric quantity for a magnetic field orientated along the generic u direction and $\max_v D(v)$ is the maximum of such a quantity obtained for $u = v$.

At this point, given the MR sequences selected for the experimental activity in section 5, it is possible to compute the I^{aniso} distribution for each implant selected in section 2. Since the maximum temperature increases obtained with the ankle plate and cranial plate were the lowest among all those simulated, and the anisotropy coefficients related to the cranial plate strongly depends on its actual shape when fitted on a specific head, the Stress Index computations have been carried out only with the hip, knee and shoulder implants. Both the Isotropic and Anisotropic Stress Indexes are represented for these implants in Figure 16. Three reference MR sequences have been considered: EPIx, EPIz and TrueFisp

Figure 16: Isotropic and Anisotropic Stress Index computed for the Hip, Knee, Knee Femoral component, Knee Tibial plate and Shoulder implant with the EPIx, EPIz and TrueFisp MR sequences. The stress index is reported in $T^2 s^{-2}$ on the $y = 0$ m slice inside the gradient coils. x - and y -axis are in meter

As done in Figure 8 of [2], by associating a suitable reference dosimetric quantity to the considered implants, it is possible to identify regions in which the implants have not to be placed in order to be scanned safely.

The proposed approach has been developed in the framework of activity A3.2.1

8 Tier 2 Experiments

Table 15 collects all the experiments carried out to investigate a correlation between the measured Stress Index with the measured maximum temperature increase. The experiments E1 for the Shoulder implants and Knee Implant Complete corresponds to the experiments E2 in Table 12 for the same implants. The experiments E1 and E3 for the Hip implant, corresponds to the experiments E2 and E3 in Table 12 for the same implant.

Accounting for the magnetic field measured in a reference point representing the position of an implant into the gradient coils, and the anisotropy coefficients computed through simulations, it is possible to compute the isotropic and anisotropic coefficients according to equations (6) and (7). The anisotropy coefficients have been computed through equation (8) using the peak temperature increase on an implant after 420 s (the duration of all experiments) of exposure to a 270 Hz harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field as the reference dosimetric quantity.

Table 16 collects for each implant, position and sequence the maximum temperature increase among the temperature channels together with the isotropic and anisotropic Stress Index associated to the relevant experiment. Both the simulated and measured maximum temperature increases are reported.

Table 15: List of experiments performed to relate the measured Stress Index with the measured maximum temperature increase

Implant	Experiment ID	Position (m)	Sequence	Duration (s)	N° sensors
Shoulder Implant	E1	-0.173, -0.003, 0.391	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Shoulder Implant	E2	-0.123, -0.003, 0.391	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Shoulder Implant	E3	-0.173, -0.003, 0.3	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Knee Implant Complete	E1	0.088, 0.009, -0.311	EPIz SR110 delay10ms	420	5
Knee Implant Complete	E2	0.141, 0.009, -0.311	EPIz SR110 delay10ms	420	5
Knee Implant Complete	E3	0.141, 0.009, -0.361	EPIz SR110 delay10ms	420	5
Hip Implant	E1	-0.092, 0.015, -0.284	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Hip Implant	E2	-0.092, 0.015, -0.284	TrueFisp SR130	420	3
Hip Implant	E3	-0.142, 0.015, -0.284	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Hip Implant	E4	-0.142, 0.015, -0.284	TrueFisp SR130	420	3
Hip Implant	E5	-0.142, 0.015, -0.334	EPIx SR110 delay10ms	420	3
Hip Implant	E6	-0.142, 0.015, -0.334	TrueFisp SR130	420	3

Table 16: Maximum simulated and measured temperature increase over the implants after 420 s of exposure together with the Isotropic and Anisotropic Stress Index associated to the relevant experiment and to the implant reference position. Both for the measurements and simulations, the maximum is intended as the maximum temperature increase among the temperature channels

Implant	Experiment ID	$\Delta T_{\max}^{\text{sim}}$ (K)	$\Delta T_{\max}^{\text{meas}}$ (K)	I^{iso} ($\text{T}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$)	I^{aniso} ($\text{T}^2 \text{s}^{-2}$)
Shoulder Implant	E1	0.53	0.60	6.87e2	5.51e2
Shoulder Implant	E2	0.31	0.35	4.09e2	3.00e2
Shoulder Implant	E3	0.42	0.44	7.63e2	3.86e2
Knee Implant Complete	E1	0.54	0.61	3.56e2	2.79e2
Knee Implant Complete	E2	0.67	0.81	4.41e2	3.46e2
Knee Implant Complete	E3	0.66	0.69	3.66e2	2.87e2
Hip Implant	E1	0.38	0.30	4.00e2	3.85e2
Hip Implant	E2	0.31	0.26	3.40e2	2.90e2
Hip Implant	E3	0.53	0.48	5.70e2	5.52e2
Hip Implant	E4	0.41	0.37	4.56e2	3.96e2
Hip Implant	E5	0.52	0.42	5.52e2	5.14e2
Hip Implant	E6	0.41	0.36	4.55e2	3.86e2

The effect of introducing the anisotropy coefficients in the Stress Index is appreciable in Figure 17 where the comparison between the simulation of the experiments carried out by MR:COMP (implementing the ISO10974 testing procedure) are compared with the peak temperature increase obtained simulating the experiments listed in Table 16. Despite being still conservative, the Anisotropic Stress Index moves the results of the realistic exposure scenarios nearer to the worst orientation experiments which are used to limit the Stress Index for safety purposes. In order to show the results for the hip implant (see Figure 17d), an additional simulation has been carried out since the hip implant was not included among the implants measured by MR:COMP in section 5.

Figure 18 highlights the correlation between the Anisotropic Stress Index and the measured temperature increase using the experiments listed in Table 15. The case of the shoulder implant, Figure 18a, is particularly interesting since it shows how the the Anisotropic Stress Index improves the correlation between the Stress Index and the maximum measured temperature increase.

Finally, Figures 19, 20 and 21 compares the measured and simulated temperature increase for the experiments of Table 15.

The results presented in this section satisfy the requirements of activity A3.2.2

Figure 17: Comparison between the results applying the ISO10974 testing procedure (from MRC simulated results) and the realistic exposure scenarios as a function of the isotropic and Anisotropic Stress Indices

Figure 18: Isotropic and anisotropic stress index vs. the measured temperature increase for the data of Table 16

(a) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch0 (b) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch1 (c) Shoulder implant - E1 - Ch2

(d) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch0 (e) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch1 (f) Shoulder implant - E2 - Ch2

(g) Shoulder implant - E3 - Ch0 (h) Shoulder implant - E3 - Ch1 (i) Shoulder implant - E3 - Ch2

Figure 19: Experiments involving the shoulder implant in three different positions. The measured temperature increase values are compared to the results obtained by means of numerical simulations. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$).

(a) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch0

(b) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch1

(c) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch3

(d) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch4

(e) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch5

(f) Knee Implant - E1 - Ch6

(g) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch0

(h) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch1

(i) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch3

(j) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch4

(k) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch5

(l) Knee Implant - E2 - Ch6

(m) Knee Implant - E3 - Ch0

(n) Knee Implant - E3 - Ch1

(o) Knee Implant - E3 - Ch3

Figure 20: Experiments involving the knee implant in three different positions. The measured temperature increase values are compared to the results obtained by means of numerical simulations. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$).

Table 17: Power deposited into the implant (W) at dB/dt equal to 42 T s^{-1} with (w/) and without (w/o) taking into account the skin effect in harmonic simulations

Frequency (Hz)	Femur			Tibial			Shoulder			Hip		
	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio
270	0.032	0.032	0.999	0.019	0.019	1.000	0.011	0.011	0.998	0.018	0.018	0.999
1750	1.338	1.273	0.952	0.788	0.775	0.984	0.478	0.454	0.949	0.765	0.716	0.936
3000	3.932	3.435	0.874	2.314	2.206	0.953	1.406	1.215	0.865	2.248	1.900	0.845

9 Simulations Accuracy

9.1 Skin effect

As the frequency increases, the skin effect is expected to change the quadratic dependance of the frequency value with the deposited power and following temperature increase. In particular, at the same dB/dt , the skin effect reduces the previous quantities leading to more safe conditions. However, when the testing is performed at a frequency where the skin effect is significant, results cannot be extrapolated to a lower frequency without underestimating both the deposited power and the temperature increase. Since it's useful to increase the frequency to relax the power requirements in experimental exposure systems to achieve a specific dB/dt , it's important to investigate the frequency value at which the skin effect starts playing a significant role.

Tables 17 and 18 report the power deposited in four specimens at three different frequencies when the skin effect is or is not considered. At a frequency of 1750 Hz (the value suggested for implant testing in the last ISO 10974 revision), the minimum ratio between powers and maximum peak temperature increases w/ and w/o skin effect is 0.936 and 0.941 for the hip implant. Since the skin effect is negligible at 270 Hz, this value also represent the ratio between the power/temperature increase of the experiment

Table 18: Maximum peak temperature increase ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) at dB/dt equal to 42 T s^{-1} with (w/) and without (w/o) taking into account the skin effect in harmonic simulations. Results refer to a 30 min heating

Frequency (Hz)	Femur			Tibial			Shoulder			Hip		
	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio
270	0.067	0.067	0.998	0.051	0.051	1.000	0.037	0.037	0.999	0.032	0.032	1.000
1750	2.807	2.650	0.944	2.122	2.084	0.982	1.544	1.465	0.949	1.350	1.271	0.941
3000	8.245	7.083	0.859	6.238	5.916	0.948	4.538	3.927	0.865	3.968	3.412	0.860

Table 19: Peak temperature increase ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) for an exposure of 420 s to an EPI sequence without (w/o) and with (w/) considering the skin effect.

Position	Shoulder (EPI _x)			Knee (EPI _z)			Hip (EPI _x)		
	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio	w/o	w/	Ratio
Pos0	0.711	0.688	0.968	0.846	0.811	0.959	0.640	0.617	0.963
Pos1	0.418	0.405	0.968	1.059	1.017	0.960	0.882	0.849	0.962
Pos2	0.567	0.550	0.971	0.995	0.954	0.959	0.856	0.824	0.963

Figure 21: Experiments involving the hip implant in three different positions. The measured temperature increase values are compared to the results obtained by means of numerical simulations. Error bars refer to the expanded uncertainty ($k = 2$).

carried out at 1750 Hz and extrapolated down to 270 Hz with the actual power/temperature increase at 270 Hz. As one can see from the tables, at 3 kHz the skin effect causes the minimum ratios to be 0.845 and 0.860 for the deposited power and maximum peak temperature increase, respectively. The trend is evident also from Figure 22, where the two curves start diverging for frequencies above 1750 Hz. Finally, Table 19 reports the peak temperature increases after 420 s of exposure to an EPI sequence with and without considering the skin effect. The implants have been simulated in three different positions and a minimum ratio between the temperature increases with and without the skin effect consideration is always above the 95 %.

(a) Femur component deposited power

(b) Femur component maximum peak temperature Increase

(c) Tibial component deposited power

(d) Tibial component maximum peak temperature increase

(e) Shoulder deposited power

(f) Shoulder maximum peak temperature increase

(g) Hip deposited power

(h) Hip maximum peak temperature increase

Figure 22: Comparison between the power and temperature simulation results with and without accounting for the skin effects at different frequencies with different implants. Results are normalized with respect to the power/temperature increase at 270 Hz without skin effect. A 30 min heating has been considered for temperature increases

9.2 Implant Components vs Entire Implant Simulations

Table 20 reports the maximum peak temperature increases and anisotropy coefficients for the knee and hip implant simulated as entire devices or separated components. The two implants have been selected since they were the only ones separated by a liner. This suggests that their components could be simulated separately. When the liner is removed a lower maximum peak temperature increase is recorded due to the different thermal exchange. Whereas the introduction of the liner leads the maximum peak temperature increase simulated with the single knee implant components to be close to that of the whole implant, this is not the case with the hip implant. In the latter case, the whole implant heats up by 23% more than the single component reaching the maximum peak temperature increase (i.e., the acetabular cup). Interestingly, the maximum peak temperature increase of the whole hip implant occurs in a point in contact with the ball. This suggests that, even if the liner is a thermal insulator, some heat is exchanged through it. From the perspective of the anisotropy coefficients (see Figures 23, 24), if single components have to be tested separately, one strategy could be to use the maximum of each single-component-with-liner η_v as representative of the whole implant anisotropy coefficients (*Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients* in Table 20). In the case of the knee implant, such a distribution is quite representative of the Anisotropy Coefficients of the complete implant. The Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) with respect to the Anisotropy Coefficients of the complete implant is equal to 0.024 and the latter exceeds the Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients by a maximum of 0.036. The same does not apply to the hip implant where the Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients distribution leads to an RMSE of 0.108 and to a significant overestimation of the Anisotropy Coefficients computed for the complete implant. Another strategy could be to weight the single-component-with-liner Anisotropy Coefficients before looking for the maximum (*Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients* in Table 20). In Table 20 and in Figures 23, 24, the weights are the ratio between the maximum peak temperature increase of the single-component-with-liner and the highest maximum peak temperature increase among those of all the single-component-with-liner composing the complete implant. This strategy slightly improves the RMSE for the hip implant (0.093) but increases the maximum difference $\Delta(\eta)$ and does not improve the results for the knee implant at all.

The results of this section refers to activity A3.2.3

10 Testing Exclusion Criteria

Three specimens have been selected among the implants identified in section 2: the cranial plate, the ankle plate and the screws. In addition, two stent models are analyzed (see Figure 25). Accounting for the ISO 10974 testing conditions, those objects do not lead to concerning peak temperature increases in their original shape and dimension due to their relatively small size. Therefore, they are good candidates for investigating the scaling factor leading to a significant peak temperature increase. As a consequence, these implants can be considered intrinsically safe wherever either such a scaling factor result in unrealistic implant dimensions or shape, or a significant peak temperature increase cannot be obtained at all. The following sections report the result with reference to a 900 s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} . All simulations have been performed in a homogeneous phantom whose properties are listed in Table 21

Cranial Plate

Table 22 collects the results relevant to the cranial plate. Each configuration is identified by a code $\langle n \rangle \times \langle n \rangle _ \langle s \rangle$, where $\langle n \rangle$ represents the number of mesh elements along one of the two grid dimensions and $\langle s \rangle$ is the cranial plate thickness. The larger plate is the only one leading to a peak temperature increase higher than 1 K. As the side or thickness decrease, also the peak temperature

Figure 23: Anisotropy Coefficients maps for the hip implant.

Figure 24: Anisotropy Coefficients maps for the knee implant.

Table 20: Maximum peak temperature increase (30 min heating) for different implant configurations. The root mean square error between the anisotropy coefficients of the complete implant (η_{complete}) and the single components of the same implant (η_{partial}) is reported. The maximum and minimum value of the difference between η_{complete} and η_{partial} , $\Delta(\eta)$ is reported as well. See the text for the meaning of "Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients" and "Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients"

Implant Configuration	Max dT @ 42 T s ⁻¹	RMSE(η)	max($\Delta(\eta)$)	min($\Delta(\eta)$)
Knee Complete	6.43 °C	-	-	-
Knee Tibial	5.81 °C	0.120	0.381	-0.020
Knee Tibial + Liner	6.16 °C	0.120	0.385	-0.015
Knee Femur	5.22 °C	0.083	0.199	-0.080
Knee Femur + Liner	5.52 °C	0.081	0.198	-0.064
Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.024	0.036	-0.064
Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.029	0.092	-0.064
MAX	6.43 °C			
Hip Complete	6.63 °C	-	-	-
Hip Acetabular Cup	4.85 °C	0.115	0.274	-0.025
Hip Acetabular Cup + Liner	5.03 °C	0.115	0.271	-0.024
Hip Stem & ball	3.58 °C	0.108	0.002	-0.172
Hip Stem & ball + Liner	3.99 °C	0.108	0.003	-0.169
Maximum Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.108	0.003	-0.169
Maximum Weighted Anisotropy Coefficients	-	0.093	0.078	-0.169
MAX	6.63 °C			

increase does. If a 1 K peak temperature increase after the 900s exposure is arbitrarily taken as safety threshold, the cranial plate cannot be considered GC intrinsically safe. Indeed, the 14×14_06 configuration corresponds to a realistic product. Furthermore, there may be cases where more cranial plates are combined together. This may be similar to a condition where a cranial plate with a side larger than 107 mm is adopted. As a consequence, each scenarios involving such an implant should be studied with respect to GC safety. Table 22 could help in this regard but one should consider the following points:

1. In the reported conditions, the magnetic field is orthogonal to the cranial plate surface and the latter lies flat in the phantom. This is unlikely the case when the implant is adopted in realistic conditions, where the cranial plate is shaped on the patient skull and the gradient magnetic field direction can be different from that leading to the highest peak temperature increase.
2. The reported experiments are carried out in a phantom whose properties complies with those

Table 21: Phantom properties

Thermal conductivity	0.624 W m ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
Heat capacity	4200 J K ⁻¹
Mass Density	1006 kg m ⁻³

(a) Model A

(b) Model B

Figure 25: Stent models considered in the analysis of A3.2.4

Table 22: Deposited power and peak temperature increase after 900 s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} for different cranial plate configurations

Configuration	Thickness (mm)	Side (mm)	Total Power (W)	Peak ΔT (K)
14×14_06	0.6	107	0.677	1.128
12×12_06	0.6	92.5	0.386	0.807
12×12_04	0.4	92.5	0.171	0.358
12×12_025	0.25	92.5	0.067	0.140
9×9_06	0.6	71.3	0.136	0.424
6×6_06	0.6	50	0.033	0.183
3×3_06	0.6	28.5	0.003	0.046

Table 23: Deposited power and peak temperature increase after 900s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} for different ankle plate configurations

Length (mm)	Volume (mm ³)	Total Surface (mm ²)	Scaling Factor	Total Power (W)	Peak ΔT (K)
258	8023.6	8715.72	1	0.268	0.226
329	16684.4	14199.2	1.5	0.912	0.528
408	31905.9	21876.1	2	2.69	1.09

Table 24: Deposited power and peak temperature increase after 900s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} for different screws

Length (mm)	Diameter (mm)	Total Power (W)	Peak ΔT (K)
60	3.65	1.3e-4	7.5e-4
60	7.13	2e-3	8.6e-3
120	3.65	2.4 e-4	8.1e-4
120	7.13	3.9e-3	8.6e-3

suggested by the ISO 10974 standard. This background is significantly different from the actual background in realistic conditions.

Ankle Plate

Table 23 reports the results for the ankle plate. Two scaling factors (1.5 and 2) have been applied to the original implant. In order to overcome the 1K peak temperature increase in worst conditions, it is required to double the original dimensions of the implant leading to an unrealistic object. Even considering the different background between phantom and realistic condition, it is unlikely this implant can lead to concerning situation as regards CG heating.

Skrews

Table 24 reports the results for different skrews. The original realistic skrew dimensions, *i.e.*, length: 60 mm, diameter: 3.65 mm, have been modified leading to other three skrew configurations. Despite their unrealistic dimensions, even the larger and longer skrews lead to very low peak temperature increases. Even considering the different background between phantom and realistic condition, it is very unlikely this specimens can lead to concerning situation as regards CG heating.

Stents

Two $\partial B/\partial t$ vector direction have been considered with respect to the sent: axial direction (Z) and transverse direction (X). Coronal stents usually range from 8 mm to 38 mm in length and from 2.5 mm to 4 mm in diameter. Biliary stents usually range from 4 mm to 120 mm in length and 8 mm to 10 mm in diameter. They are usually made of Nitinol wire whose diameter goes from 0.2 mm to 0.6 mm. Tables 25 and 26 collect the results for the two models of the stents and for different diameters of the wires. The negligible peak temperature increases suggest that also the stents are not a safety concern from the gradient heating point of view.

The results presented in this section refers to the avtivity A3.2.4

Table 25: Deposited power and peak temperature increase after 900 s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} for different configurations of the model A of the stents

$\partial B/\partial t$ Direction	\varnothing Wire (mm)	\varnothing Stent (mm)	Length (mm)	Total Power (W)	Peak ΔT (K)
X	0.2	7	13	9.538e-06	0.269e-3
X	0.4	7	13	3.815e-05	1.075e-3
X	0.6	7	13	8.584e-05	2.419e-3
X	0.6	10	30	4.505e-04	6.658e-03
X	0.6	10	60	1.063e-03	8.382e-03
X	0.6	10	120	2.617e-03	12.45e-3
Z	0.2	7	13	1.099e-05	0.242e-3
Z	0.4	7	13	4.397e-05	0.969e-3
Z	0.6	7	13	9.893e-05	2.181e-3

Table 26: Deposited power and peak temperature increase after 900 s exposure to a harmonic, homogeneous magnetic field, with a $\partial B/\partial t$ of 42 T s^{-1} for different configurations of the model B of the stents

$\partial B/\partial t$ Direction	\varnothing Wire (mm)	\varnothing Stent (mm)	Length (mm)	Total Power (W)	Peak ΔT (K)
X	0.2	9	57	4.102e-04	3.363e-3
X	0.4	9	57	1.641e-03	13.45e-3
X	0.6	9	57	3.692e-03	30.26e-3
Z	0.2	9	57	5.627e-04	3.458e-3
Z	0.4	9	57	2.251e-03	13.83e-3
Z	0.6	9	57	5.064e-03	31.12e-3

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